

Wikipedia Day 2020: Wikidata for librarians

Slides available at
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Hello from School of Data Science

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Agenda

1. Celebration!
2. Introduction to Wikidata
3. Wikidata for librarians
4. Wikidata for librarians in Virginia

Summary of asks

1. Celebrate Wikipedia's birthday & Public Domain Day
2. General awareness of Wikipedia / Wikidata as a general reference resource
3. University libraries make a norm of
 - a. curating and sharing lists of researchers
 - b. and those people's publications
4. Libraries grow to align themselves with data management best practices

Happy Birthday and Public Domain Day

Happy Birthday Wikipedia!

- January 15, 2001 incorporation
- top-ten website since ~2005
- now available in ca. 300 languages
- 1 billion annual unique visitors
- general reference source
- teaches citations
- friend to librarians

WIKIPEDIA

Happy Birthday Creative Commons!

- January 15, 2001 website registration
- digital reuse agreements
- universal standard
- teaches copyright

Happy Birthday Public Domain Day!

- January 1, 2019 first celebration in US since Internet culture
- works in 1924 = public domain
- 1 year of data and media, annually, forever

**Wikipedia is most requested,
published, accessed, and
consulted source of information
on almost every topic it covers**

We are all in the media business

Attention is the new currency

What is Wikidata?

Wikidata is...

- open
- FAIR
- designed for Internet
- supporting research
- marketing outreach
- integrated into Google, Siri etc

Association of Research Libraries Whitepaper on Wikidata

**"Give staff time to
experiment and
contribute to
Wikidata"**

ARL White Paper on Wikidata
Opportunities and Recommendations

April 18, 2019

/ ASSOCIATION
OF RESEARCH
LIBRARIES /

Wikidata for people

Kathryn C. Thornton,
University of
Virginia astronaut

born - 1952

nationality - American

school - UVA PhD 1979

occupation - physicist

time in space - 40 days

Wikidata for places

University of Virginia

endowment - 9.6b

budget - 1.4b

Pres - James Ryan

academics - 2,102

students - 24,360

Wikidata for medicine

gout

specialty - rheumatology

symptoms - swelling

onset - older males

causes - uric acid

risk - diet, alcohol

Wikidata content

publications

miscellaneous

???

people

taxon

territory

structure

event

Example use case:
What is the most populous city with a female mayor?

Data you need:

1. List of all (current) cities
2. (current) population of every city
3. (current) mayors of every city
4. (current) gender of every mayor

Wikidata Query Service

The screenshot shows the Wikidata Query Service interface. At the top, there is a header with the Wikidata logo, the text "Wikidata Query Service", and three buttons: "Examples", "Help", and "More tools". Below the header is a text area containing a SPARQL query. The query is as follows:

```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?city ?cityLabel ?mayor ?mayorLabel WHERE
2 {
3     ?city wdt:P31/wdt:P279* wd:Q515 . # find instances of subclasses of city
4     ?city p:P6 ?statement . # with a P6 (head of government) statement
5     ?statement ps:P6 ?mayor . # ... that has the value ?mayor
6     ?mayor wdt:P21 wd:Q6581072 . # ... where the ?mayor has P21 (sex or gender) female
7     FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?statement pq:P582 ?x } # ... but the statement has no P582 (end date) qualifier
8     # Now select the population value of the ?city
9     # (wdt: properties use only statements of "preferred" rank if any, usually meaning "current population")
10    ?city wdt:P1082 ?population .
11    # Optionally, find English labels for city and mayor:
12    SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en" .| }
13 }
14 ORDER BY DESC(?population)
15 LIMIT 10
```

On the left side of the interface, there is a vertical toolbar with several icons: an information icon, a search icon, a pin icon, a diamond icon, a folder icon, a refresh icon, a trash icon, and a link icon. At the bottom left, there is a blue play button icon.

Answer

1. Tokyo Yuriko Koike
2. Mexico City Claudia Sheinbaum
3. Hong Kong Carrie Lam
4. Bogotá Claudia López Hernández
5. Baghdad Zekra Alwach

Lexemes across languages

Words derived from the Proto-Indo-European word **wódr̥*, including the English “water”

Language support continuously expanding

**On what topics
do researchers
at your
university
publish?**

Evolution of content related to UVA

For University of Virginia

1. high energy physics
2. myocardial infarction
3. teenager
4. Higgs boson
5. Bangladesh

<https://w.wiki/FCC>

For JMU

1. citizen science
2. quasar
3. borderline personality disorder
4. swallowing
5. telomere length

<https://w.wiki/FCK>

For GMU

1. teenager
2. obesity
3. attention
4. Sierra Leone
5. climate change

<https://w.wiki/FCM>

For Virginia Tech

1. phylogenetics
2. condensed matter physics
3. Sarcocystis neurona
4. microfluidics
5. autism spectrum disorder

<https://w.wiki/FCY>

For VCU

1. schizophrenia
2. teenager
3. alcohol consumption
4. genome-wide association study
5. alcoholism

<https://w.wiki/FCb>

For University of Richmond

1. bias
2. visualization
3. *saccharomyces cerevisiae*
4. alcohol consumption
5. *Caenorhabditis elegans*

<https://w.wiki/FCCc>

ORCID

1. compiles open data profiles of people
2. established nonprofit project
3. already in use at UVA

ORCID use

- ◻ in the US
- ◻ across Virginia
- ◻ at UVA

Usage history in Wikidata

WikiCite and Scholia

- WikiCite: curating bibliographic metadata via Wikidata
- Scholia: visualizations of WikiCite data; can be linked from Wikipedia

Scholia profile examples

- Topics, e.g. Zika virus
- Organizations, e.g. GMU
- Individuals, e.g. VCU's Danielle Dick
- Combinations, e.g. machine learning in Copenhagen

Comparison UVA/ JMU/ GMU/ VT/ VCU/ UR

Citations to works ratio

The ratio between the number of citations received and the works authored per organization per year.

Thanks!

Any questions?

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Credits

Special thanks to all the people who made and released these awesome resources for free:

- ⬡ Presentation template by [SlidesCarnival](#)
- ⬡ Icons from Nounproject